

SHORT COMMUNICATION

EVALUATION OF THE REPRODUCTIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF TWO SUBSPECIES OF AFRICAN GIANT LAND SNAILS *Archachatina marginata ovum* AND *Archachatina marginata saturalis* FED OIL PALM FRUITS IN SWAMP FOREST ZONE OF NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

The study evaluated the reproductive characteristics of two African giant land snail subspecies (*Archachatina marginata ovum* and *Archachatina marginata saturalis*) fed oil palm fruits in swamp forest zone of Nigeria within a 20 week periods. Reproductive characteristics of the two African giant land snails subspecies evaluated revealed that *Archachatina marginata ovum* performed better ($P < 0.05$) than *Archachatina marginata saturalis* in terms of total number of eggs laid, clutch size, incubation period, percent egg hatchability, egg weight, egg length and egg width.

KEYWORDS: Giant land snails, subspecies, reproductive characteristics

INTRODUCTION

The African giant land snail is distributed all over the swamp forest zones of Africa. This snail species according to Akinnusi (2004), Ogogo (2004); Ibom (2009) is native to Nigeria but has spread to other African countries and beyond, south east Abia and the pacific islands through commerce (Payne and Wilson, 1999). Captivity is attracting the keen interest of both scientist and farmers, suggesting the potentials of these subspecies as snails for commercial farming in the humid tropics (Ubuja, 2011). The survival, growth, development and reproduction of snails like that of other animal species depend highly on the quality of feed consumed (Hodasi 1982). The population explosion implies that many people require the supply of protein in their diet because of its important role in human well being which includes growth, maintenance of hormonal and enzymatic activities and improvement of the defence mechanism of the body (Ademolu *et al.*, 2004). Information on the two snail subspecies in terms of their reproductive characteristics in the swamp forest zone for snail farmers is minimal. The current study focuses on evaluating the reproductive characteristics of two subspecies of African giant land snail fed oil palm fruits, thus recommending the best subspecies for a profitable snail farm in swamp forest zone of Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in the snailery unit of the Animal science, Department, University of Calabar, Cross River State. The experimental materials used in this study were snails, cages, soil, oil palm fruits. Cages were constructed with wood and wire guaze. Dimensions of the cages were 45cm (length) x 45cm (width) x 40cm (height). Loamy soil was collected, loosened and sterilized to kill all organisms (insects). Sterilization of soil was done by heating the soil. Loamy soil was preferred for neutral to slightly alkaline pH Soils. The Choice of feed for this study was oil palm fruits. This is regarded as a conventional feed of snails (Ogogo 2004, Omole *et al.*, 2007). The experimental snails consisted of two classes of snail for data collection. The classes were adult *Archachatina marginata ovum* and *Archachatina marginata saturalis*. A total of eighty (80)) sexually matured snails were used in this study, forty (40) snails each of *Archachatina marginata ovum* and *Archachatina marginata saturalis*. Twenty (20) snails from each species of the snails were allotted to the treatment diet which was replicated 4 times with 5 snails per replicate. The snails were fed with oil palm fruits.

Data on reproductive parameters were allotted on weekly basis for a period of 20 weeks. Data collected included total number of eggs land, clutch size, incubation period, percent egg hatchability egg weight, egg

length, egg width. T-test was used to analyze the reproductive parameters of the two subspecies and the means separated using Fisher's Least Significant Difference (LSD).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of reproductive performance of the two subspecies of snail are shown in Table 1. The results showed that *Archachatina marginata ovum* laid more eggs (77) than *Archachatina marginata saturalis* which laid Forty (40) eggs .

The findings here are similar to reports of Ubuja *et al.* (2011) on *Archachatina marginata ovum*. These observations on prolificacy could be due to inherent genetic potential of the snails. Similarly, Ubuja *et al.* (2011) observed that eggs laid by *Archachatina marginata ovum* are relatively larger in size than those laid by *Archachatina marginata saturalis* probably because of size of breed. The number of eggs laid per clutch by *Archachatina marginata ovum* fed oil palm fruits were significantly ($P < 0.05$) different from *Archachatina marginata saturalis* . High clutch sizes observed in this study by *Archachatina marginata ovum* than *Archachatina marginata ovum* than *Archachatina marginata saturalis* may be as a result of their genetic make up, size and breed of snails as well as haemolymph characteristics. This agrees with Ibom *et al* (2008) that there is variation in reproductive activities between subspecies of a particular breed. However, *Archachatina marginata ovum* recorded high clutch size (Table 1). Okon *et al.* (2009) reported that age and environment can influence egg and clutch size of snail. The mean clutch size of *Archachatina marginata ovum* in this study (Table 1) is lower than reports by Awesu (1980) and Amubode (1994). In the same vain, mean clutch observed in this study is higher than those recorded by Ogogo (1989), Adegbaaju (2000). The mean clutch size of *Archachatina marginata saturalis* (Table 1) is lower than reports of Payne and Wilson (1999), Ejidike *et al.* (2002), Ogogo (1989). The mean incubation period of this study indicated that *Archachatina marginata ovum* subspecies had the highest incubation period of 40.57 days which was statistically ($P < 0.05$) different from that of *Archachatina marginata saturalis* (30.30 days). The variation in incubation period could be differences in genetic composition, breed, environmental and soil condition, such as temperature, relative humidity and soil composition. Differences in incubation periods between the two subspecies confirmed that snails incubation period vary with species (Ogogo 2004). The values obtained in this study indicated that incubation period of *Archachatina marginata ovum* (Table 1) is higher than values reported by Awesu (1980), Elmshie (1982), Mfon (1986) Okon *et al* (2009), Ubuja (2012). Ibom *et al* (2008) reported incubation periods from 14 – 28 days for *Archachatina marginata ovum* which are lower than the mean values obtained in this study (Table 1). the mean incubation period recorded *Archachatina marginata saturalis* is higher than the reports of Cobbina (1993), Stievenant (1996), Amusan and Onudiji (1998). The result in Table 1 indicated that mean percent egg hatchability of *Archachatina marginata ovum* is 84.52% while *Archachatina marginata saturalis* had 80.83%. These values showed significant ($P < 0.05$) differences between percent egg hatchability of both subspecies fed oil palm fruits. The variation in percent egg hatchability between these subspecies may be differences in incubation period and size of eggs. These results agreed with the results of Okon *et al.* (2010) that disparities in percent egg hatchability may be a result of snail breed, size of snail and size of eggs. Mean percent egg hatchability (Table 1) of *Archachatina marginata ovum* is higher than 68.4%, 70.0% and 72.32% reported by Ogogo (1989), Akinnuusi (2004) and Ubuja (2012), respectively. On the contrary, mean percent egg hatchability of *Archachatina marginata saturalis* in this study is similar to the values reported by Ibom *et al.* (2008), Ewa (2007) and Odido (2007). The results in Table 1 indicated than mean egg weight of *Archachatina marginata ovum* is 1.73 a while *Archachatina marginata saturalis* had 1.57g values of egg weight in both subspecies were significantly ($P < 0.05$) different on oil palm fruits. Disparity could be that as hatching days keep decreasing during incubation, the egg weight also decreases. The decreases in egg weight may be caused by environmental conditions. This observation agrees with reports of Ibom *et al.* (2008) that a decrease in egg weight is attributed to exposure to relative humidity and temperature as well as soil condition which differ from the near constant material (uterine) environment which they belong before lay. Mean egg weight of *Archachatina marginata ovum* in this study is larger than values reported by Ibom *et al.* (2008) and Okon *et al.* (2009) in white-skinned ectotype of the same subspecies. In contrast Ogogo 1989, 2004) obtained higher values in *Archachatina e marginata saturalis*. Results in Table 1 showed that mean egg length of *Archachatina marginata ovum* is 15.59mm while *Archachatina marginata saturalis* had 14.10mm.

These values showed significant ($P < 0.05$) differences between egg lengths of both subspecies on oil palm fruits. Differences egg length between these subspecies could be attributed to breed differences. These results agreed with reports of Ibom *et al.* (2008) that differences in egg length may be caused by breed effect, soil

texture, genetic make up. Mean egg length (Table I) of *Archachatina marginata ovum* is higher than 1.48mm and 14.32mm reported by Ibom *et al* (2008) and Okon *et al.* (2010), respectively. On the contrary mean egg length of *Archachatina marginata saturalis* in this study is lower than the values reported by Amubode (1994) and Awesu (1980). Results in Table 1 indicated that mean egg width of *Archachatina marginata ovum* is 13.53mm while *Archachatina marginata saturalis* had 12.13mm. These values showed significant ($P > 0.05$) differences between egg width of both subspecies fed oil palm fruits. Variation in egg width between these two subspecies may be due to age and size of the snails. These results agreed with reports of Okon *et al.* (2010) that differences in egg width exist among snails and may be caused by size of the snails, incubation condition such as water uptake. The values obtained in this study indicated that egg width of *Archachatina marginata ovum* (Table 1) is higher than 10.78mm reported by Okon *et al* (2010). Results of egg width in *Archachatina marginata saturalis* (Table 1) were lower than 16mm (Awesu, 1980).

CONCLUSION

The result of this study however evaluated the high reproductive potential of *Archachatina marginata ovum* and revealed that this subspecies is prolific and can perform better than *Archachatina marginata saturalis* in terms of their reproductive characteristics when fed oil palm fruits.

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Table 1. Reproductive Evaluation of adult snails of *Archachatina marginata ovum* and *Archachatina marginata saturalis* fed oil palm fruits for 20 weeks

Parameters	<i>Archachatina marginata ovum</i>	<i>Archachatina marginata saturalis</i>	SEM
Total number of eggs laid	77	40	
Mean Clutch size	7.70 ^a	5.00 ^b	0.99
Mean incubation Period (days)	40.57 ^a	30.30 ^b	0.29
Mean percent egg hatchability (%)	84.52 ^a	80.83 ^b	4.12
Mean egg weight (g)	1.73 ^a	1.57 ^b	0.06
Mean egg length at lay (mm)	15.59 ^a	14.10 ^b	0.34
Mean egg width at lay (mm)	13.53 ^a	12.13 ^b	0.29

SEM= standard error of mean

^{ab}Mean values with different superscript in the same row are significantly (P<0.05) different.

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